

CONSEQUENCES OF COMMUNAL CONFLICT IN MBO LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA OF AKWA IBOM STATE

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ABSTRACT

This descriptive research examined the consequences of communal conflict in Mbo Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. A survey research design was adopted by the researcher for the study. The researcher made use of the Marxist Conflict Theory as a framework. Study participants were randomly selected from Afaha Okpo District, Effiat District, Nkwong District Ibiaku District, Ikpo Ikono District, and Ikpa Ibom District. A simple random sampling method drew a sample size of 625 participants. Data were collected through the Mbo Conflict and Mediation Test and Analysis Data Collection Instrument" (MCMTADCI). Socio-demographic data collected were presented in a table using simple percentages. Data collected were analysed descriptively using SPSS to analyse with simple frequency and percentage tables. The study's findings revealed that burning of houses, killing of innocent citizens, destruction of people's properties, destruction of businesses, destruction of farmlands, kidnapping of innocent citizens, looting of people's properties and raping of women and girls are consequences of communal conflict in Mbo Local Government Area. The researcher recommended among others recommended that the government should educate the people of Mbo Local Government Area on the needs to live in unity and the consequences of communal conflict.

KEYWORDS: Communal conflict, consequences of conflict, Mbo, and killing of innocent citizens

INTRODUCTION

Communal conflict has been a result of clashes of interests based on cultural, traditional, ancestral, political, economic or personal driven values among people of common geographical habitations and boundaries. Conflict is communal when it involves lives and properties of groups of individuals within the context of the clash of interest. Interests remain the underlying factor in conflict. Communal conflicts are results of social relations within human groupings (Oji, Innocent, and Nwoba, 2014). Communal conflict is ideologically a

conflict that arises between two or more communities within common boundaries, and as a result of clashes of interest of engaging communities. Communal conflict is a disagreement between two or more communities (Oji, Innocent, and Nwoba, 2014). Communal conflict is a situation that underscored the importance of components like place, interaction and subsistence which are the elements of communal life (Ilvento, 1995 cited in Oji, Innocent, and Nwoba, 2014). Communal conflict is defined as a conflict between non-state groups that are organized along a shared communal identity (Brosché, 2015).

Communal conflict has been a collective violence that often instigates civil war among human groups of common boundaries and geo-location (Fearon and Laitin 2011). Communal conflicts have over the ages pose a severe threat to human safety, existence, security, and the killing of thousands of people each year (Sundberg, Eck, and Kreutz 2012). Communal conflict has been responsible for much destruction of lives, properties, and relationship among warring human groups especially in the Sub-Saharan Africa. Communal conflicts are threat or action of one party directed at the territory, rights, interests or privileges of another party, because of differences over economic issues, power or authority, cultural values and beliefs (Oji, Innocent, and Nwoba, 2014) which are in some cases initiated by some of the traditional leaders (Peters and Bassey, 2019)

Conflict itself is an extreme irrational and forceful indication of interest of one human group over the other based on certain factorial considerations. Humans live in a socio-physical environment through dependence and interdependence relationships which often produces contradictions and conflicts (Oji, Innocent, and Nwoba, 2014). Conflict is perceived by as any unconformities situation whereby incompatible activities, feelings or intentions take place (Gale Encyclopedia 1998 cited in Osagea, Funmilayob, Fredc and Samuel, 2010).

Conflict is pervasive and inevitable because of its emergence due to interaction among group of people. The emergence or manifestation of conflicts is a constant factor that it is ever present in social relations (Alimba, 2014). Conflict is an experience of struggle between two or more independent individuals or group of people over perceived incompatible differences in beliefs, values, and goal, or differences in desire for esteem, control and connectedness (Wilmot and Hocker, 2011). Conflict can also refer to the contradictions that arise from the differences in the interest, ideas, ideologies, orientations and precipitous tendencies of the people involve (Onwe, Nwogbaga and Nwakamma, 2015). Conflicts find expressions in many ways which include physical assault to persons, property, accusations, threats, murder, denial and avoidance (Osagea, Funmilayob, Fredc and Samuel, 2010).

The world has been plagued with disputes, and there is need to resolve these disagreements through the introduction of the third party as an intervention option for negotiation toward helping conflicting parties to come up with acceptable and consensus solution. This needed resolving mechanism is known as conflict management. Thakore (2013) refer to conflict management as both strategies and approaches of containing (managing the conflict) as well as to strategies and approaches of resolving it. The purpose of conflict management according to Thaoke (2013) whether undertaken by the parties in conflict or whether involving the intervention of an outside party, is to affect the entire structure of a conflict situation to contain the destructive components in the conflict process which may involve hostility or use of violence, and help the parties possessing incompatible goals to find some solution to their conflict.

Conflict management is a process of reducing the negative and destructive capacity of

conflict through some measures by working with the parties in conflict (Christian-Radu, 2022). The term conflict management predisposes that, conflict is inevitable and is not all conflict that can be resolved, therefore, the need to manage and regulate it (Ramsbotham, Woodhouse, and Miall (2011) cited in Christia-Radu (2022). Management of conflict entails different forms of resolution which include mediation, arbitration, conciliation and consultation (Thaoke, 2013). Conflict management is also concerned with accommodating, avoiding, collaborating, competing and compromising (Benoliel, 2023).

As a matter of fact, man in a socio-physical environment lives in continuous process of dependence and interdependence which often produces contradictions and conflicts (Oji, Innocent, and Nwoba, 2014). Conflict has been part of human and such has been the case is the case among the Niger Delta region which Mbo Local Government Area in Akwa Ibom State is part of the region. The effects of conflicts can be destructive beyond expectations of the parties involve. The results of conflicts have forced conflict management as a process aimed at resolving conflict through constructive means, and as multi-faceted in that it is applicable to many types of conflicts. Conflict in most cases that involve ethnic conflict, panels or committees are usually set up to investigate communal clashes identify the underlying causes of the conflict and address them through guiding the parties towards solutions that are mutually satisfactory, self-perpetuating, and sustaining (Raimi 2010). The rise in conflicts among warring communities in Mbo Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State have led to many regretful results with loss of lives and properties, and the needs for peaceful coexistence among the people of the area is the need to assess the cause of conflicts, the effects of these conflicts, and the management processes engaged by the people and government toward peaceful resolution and maintenance of peace within the local government area which is the gap to be filled by this study.

The African continent has continually experienced communal conflicts as one of the major recurring problems which have contributed to the underdevelopment status of the continent and economical backwardness experienced within the continent by most of the nations. Communal conflict has gradually becomes one of the cultural element of some of the people in some countries in some regions of Africa (Oji, Innocent, and Nwoba, 2014). This destructive phenomenon is not new to the African people especially among the multi-ethnic nationalities and socio-cultural complex societies, and language groups as found within the geographical setting called Nigeria. Conflict, generally is an occurring phenomenon in social relations across multi-ethnic nationalities or groups (Oji, Innocent and Nwoba, 2014). The incident of conflict at any level of occurrence arises as a result of clashes of interests, desires, goals and values aspirations in the competition for resources to meet up certain demands to find satisfaction on social life in a defined socio-physical environment (Otite, 2001). The traditional institution having a role in this which always lead to the underdevelopment of the community (Peters, Basse & Usoro, 2020)

Nigeria in pre-colonial and colonial era had experienced inter-kingdom dynastic feuds, and inter-community conflicts (Ogban-Iyam, 2005 cited in Oji, Innocent, and Nwoba, 2014). In the post-colonial Nigeria, many contemporary Nigerian communities have experienced several cases of communal conflicts, and some of the most notable examples include the Zango-Kataf conflict in Kaduna State (1999-2001); Tiv-Jukun Wukari conflict in Taraba State (1999-2001); Itsekiri-Urhobo Warri crisis, (1999-2000); Yelwa-Shendam conflict (2003-2005), Mangu-Bokoss crisis(1988-1999), the Ife-Modakeke crisis (1999-2000) (Oji,

Innocent, and Nwoba, 2014). A common feature of these conflicts according to Oji, Innocent, and Nwoba (2014) is that it has to do with their confrontational and violent dimension which led to the loss of lives and property of people who by social-relations have lived together in relative harmony. According to Peters *et al.*, (2023), it complicates social order.

Mbo Local Government Area was affected by intra- and inter-communal tensions in 2012-2013. In May 2012, Ebughu and Effiat communities clashed, reportedly killing one. In January 2013, seven reportedly died in a separate clash over farming land. In March 2013, there was a reported clash in Unyenge community. In November 2013, two women were killed in a renewed clash among Effiat communities. The communal conflicts in Mbo Local Government Area have shown how communal peaceful co-existence in socio-cultural harmony could be ruptured with attendant disastrous phenomenon with consequences on the social, cultural and political life of Mbo people in Akwa Ibom State. Lives have been lost and properties have been destroyed through communal conflicts in Mbo Local Government Area. The conflicts that arose from competing for natural resources and other interests in Mbo have brought about loss of human resources, natural resources, and physical resources. Many people have been forced out of their homes and peaceful social relationships have been interrupted by the clashes of interests, leaving Mbo Local Government Area in need of constant efficient conflict management. On this backdrop, this study seeks to examine the consequences communal conflicts in Mbo Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State which is the identifiable gap.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Conflict Theory

Conflict theory, first developed by Karl Marx, is a theory that society is in a state of perpetual conflict because of competition for limited resources. Conflict theory holds that social order is maintained by domination and power, rather than by consensus and conformity. According to conflict theory, those with wealth and power try to hold on to it by any means possible, chiefly by suppressing the poor and powerless. A basic premise of conflict theory is that individuals and groups within society will work to try to maximize their own wealth and power.

According to Investopedia (2022), Conflict theory has sought to explain a wide range of social phenomena, including wars, revolutions, poverty, discrimination, and domestic violence. It ascribes most of the fundamental developments in human history, such as democracy and civil rights, to capitalistic attempts to control the masses (as opposed to a desire for social order). Central tenets of conflict theory are the concepts of social inequality, the division of resources, and the conflicts that exist among different socioeconomic classes. The central tenets of conflict theory can explain many types of societal conflicts throughout history. Some theorists believe, as Marx did, that societal conflict is the force that ultimately drives change and development in society.

Marx's version of conflict theory focused on the conflict between two primary classes. Each class consists of a group of people bound by mutual interests and a certain degree of property ownership. Marx theorized about the bourgeoisie, a group that represented members of society who hold the majority of the wealth and means. The proletariat is the other group: It includes those considered working-class or poor.

Investopedia reports that with the rise of capitalism, Marx theorized that the

bourgeoisie, a minority within the population, would use their influence to oppress the proletariat, the majority class. This way of thinking is tied to a common image associated with conflict theory-based models of society; adherents to this philosophy tend to believe in a pyramid arrangement in terms of how goods and services are distributed in society. At the top of the pyramid is a small group of elites that dictate terms and conditions to the larger portion of society because they have an outsized amount of control over resources and power. Uneven distribution within society was predicted to be maintained through ideological coercion; the bourgeoisie would force acceptance of the current conditions by the proletariat. Conflict theory assumes that the elite will set up systems of laws, traditions, and other societal structures in order to further support their own dominance while preventing others from joining their ranks (Investopedia, 2022).

Marx theorized that, as the working class and poor were subjected to worsening conditions, a collective consciousness would raise more awareness about inequality, and this would potentially result in revolt. If, after the revolt, conditions were adjusted to favour the concerns of the proletariat, the conflict circle would eventually repeat but in the opposite direction. The bourgeoisie would eventually become the aggressor and revolter, grasping for the return of the structures that formerly maintained their dominance.

METHODOLOGY

Figure 1: Geographical location of Mbo Local Government Area (Hogan, 2022)

This study will be conducted in Mbo Local Government Area. Mbo Local Government Area is one of the five Oron people Local Government in Akwa Ibom State. The study population which is Mbo Local Government Area population according to the projected population size by 2018 is 152,610 (Akwa Ibom State Demographic Profile, 2018). The sample for this study consisted of mature adults aged between 18 years and above, who were randomly selected across randomly selected communities in Mbo Local Government Area. Data for this study was collected by the researcher who was assisted by three (3) research

assistants. The data collected in this study from the questionnaire which were formulated relatively to each research question, were analysed through the use of the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS).

RESULT

Data Presentation and Analysis

Table 1: Socio-demographic characteristics of respondents (N=625)

Demographic profile		Frequency(N)	Percentage (%)
Sex	Male	412	65.9
	Female	213	34.1
Age	18 – 25 years	118	18.9
	26 – 33 years	199	31.8
	34 – 41 years	187	29.9
	42 – 49 years	75	12.0
	50 and above	46	7.4
Marital Status	Single	213	34.1
	Married	167	26.7
	Divorced	49	7.8
	Separated	68	10.9
	Widowed	96	15.4
Highest Educational Qualification	Cohabiting	32	5.1
	No Formal Education	86	13.8
	Primary Education	128	20.5
	Post Primary Education	290	46.4
Religious Affiliation	Tertiary Education	121	19.4
	Catholic	112	17.9
	Protestant	133	21.3
	Pentecostal	311	49.8
	Islam	0	0.0
Sc	Traditional religion	46	7.4
	Other(s)	23	3.7

Table 1 shows the frequency analysis of the socio-demographic distribution of the sampled respondents. Table 4.1, indicates that the total number of study participants was 625, the males constituted 412 (65.9%) and the female constituted 213 (34.1%) female. This implies that the views expressed in this study represent both male and female, with the male study respondents in the majority. It also indicates that most of the study respondents were aged 26 – 33 (199/31.8%) years. This is followed by the study respondents who are aged 34 - 41 (187/29.9%). The study respondents who are aged 18 – 25 (118/18.9%) were the next. The next age cohort of the study respondents was 42 – 49 (75/12.0), and those aged 50 years and above (46/7.4%) were of the least age cohort. Under the marital status of the study respondents, the majority 213 (34.1%) were singles, 167 (26.7%) of the study respondents were married, 96 (15.4%) of the study respondents were widowed, 68 (10.9%) of study respondents were

separated, 49 (7.8%) of the study respondents were divorced and the least in this group were cohabitating with 32 (5.1%). For the highest educational qualification, the majority of the study respondents 290 (46.4%) were in post-primary school. This was followed by 128 (20.5%) who were in primary education, 121 (19.4%) were in tertiary education and the least in this group were of no formal education 86 (13.8%). The Pentecostals were the majority for the religious affiliation, with 311 (49.8%). This was followed by the protestants with 133 (21.3%), the Catholics were the next with 112 (17.9%), traditional religion affiliates were the next with 46 (7.4%), 23 (3.7%) were of other religion while none of the study respondents were of Islam.

Table 2: Participants' Responses on Consequences of Conflicts in Mbo Local Government Area

Consequences of conflicts in Mbo Local Government Area

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Burnt houses	394	62.7	63.0	63.0
Killing of innocent citizens	109	17.4	17.4	80.5
Destruction of properties	28	4.5	4.5	85.0
Destruction of businesses	20	3.2	3.2	88.2
Kidnapping of innocent citizens	28	4.5	4.5	92.6
Looting of people's properties	18	2.9	2.9	95.5
Destruction of farmlands	12	1.9	1.9	97.4
Raping of women and girls	16	2.5	2.6	100.0
Total	625	99.5	100.0	
Missing System	3	.5		
Total	628	100.0		

Source: Hogan, 2024

Table 2 shows the SPSS frequency analysis of the responses of the study participants on the consequences of conflicts in the Mbo Local Government Area in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. Their responses were used to investigate the impact of conflict among the Mbo people in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. Table 2, indicates that the majority of the study participants 394 (62.7%) believed that houses are burnt in Mbo Local Government Area during communal conflicts. This is followed by 109 (17.4%) who believed that the killing of innocent citizens is another

key consequence of conflict within the local government area. 28 (4.5%) of the study participants through their responses thought that the destruction of properties and kidnapping of innocent citizens were the consequences of conflict in Mbo. 20 (3.2%) of the study participants were of the opinion that conflicts in Mbo Local Government Area always lead to destruction of businesses. 18 (2.9%) of the study participants believed that people's properties are looted during communal conflicts in Mbo Local Government Area while, 16 (2.5%) of the study participants are of the thought that women and girls are raped during communal conflict in Mbo Local Government Area. 12 (1.9%) of the study participants were of the opinion that farmlands are destroyed during communal conflicts in Mbo Local Government Area.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Findings of the study also revealed that there are negative consequences of communal conflict faced by the people of Mbo Local Government Service of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. According to findings, these consequences include but are not limited to burning of houses, killing of innocent citizens, destruction of people's properties, destruction of businesses, destruction of farmlands, kidnaping of innocent citizens, looting of people's properties and raping of women and girls. These findings revealed that communal conflicts are unpleasant scenarios that are always producing unpleasant results. These findings are in terms with the position of Brosche (2015) who reported that in Congo DRC, the Ituri region of the Democratic Republic of Congo (DRC) is a well-known example of communal conflicts have killed thousands in this region. Findings also agree with Sundberg *et al.*, (2012) who posit that communal conflicts pose a severe threat to human security and kill thousands of people each year. Findings agree with Fearon and Latin (2011) who posit that this type of violence is often a trigger of civil war. The Mbo Local Government Area conflict communal situation according to findings, agrees with ACLED (2015), in some rural communities in Benue State, recently where unknown gunmen stirred up clashes between the Fulani herdsmen and the citizens, where innocent people were killed, properties destroyed, houses burnt, properties looted, women and girls raped and farmlands destroyed.

CONCLUSION

During communal conflict in Mbo Local Government Area, the people suffer a lot of consequences which include; burning of houses, killing of innocent citizens, destruction of people's properties, destruction of businesses, destruction of farmlands, kidnaping of innocent citizens, looting of people's properties and raping of women and girls. calling for meetings, discussion of key factors in the conflict, negotiation of interests, dialogue with warring stakeholders, identifying point/s of disagreement and grievances, bridging the social gap by consultation of elders, and displacement of people are the identified approaches adopted by the people of Mbo Local Government Area in conflict management processes toward attaining conflict resolution.

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